

Inseason Harvest and Effort Estimates for the 2024 Kuskokwim River Subsistence Salmon Fisheries During Block Openings

by

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ABSTRACT

Management of subsistence fisheries for salmon (*Oncorhynchus* spp.) in the Kuskokwim River has historically been conducted with minimal inseason harvest information. Due to this lack of information, managers have faced challenges making well-supported and defensible inseason decisions regarding fishing opportunities that simultaneously achieve conservation and subsistence harvest objectives, particularly during years of weak Chinook Salmon (*O. tshawytscha*) runs. In response to conservation concerns for the 2024 Kuskokwim River Chinook and Chum (*O. keta*) salmon runs, as well as for Coho Salmon (*O. kisutch*) following weak returns in 2022, the Kuskokwim River Inter-Tribal Fish Commission (KRITFC), in collaboration with the United States Fish and Wildlife Service–Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge (USFWS), the Orutsararmiut Native Council (ONC), and independent contractors collected and processed data to produce inseason subsistence salmon harvest estimates from the mainstem Kuskokwim River within the boundaries of the Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge, between and including the villages of Eek and Tuluksak. Input data included: drift and set gillnet counts from aerial surveys; subsistence harvester interviews by ONC at the Bethel boat harbor (with some support from KRITFC and USFWS) and Bethel-area fish camps, and by USFWS and KRITFC at the Bethel boat harbor; and subsistence harvester interviews by KRITFC community-based harvest monitors from the Lower Kuskokwim River villages of Eek, Tuntutuliak, Napakiak, Napaskiak, Kwethluk, Akiachak, Akiak, and Tuluksak. Using methods developed and refined during 2016–2023, the best minimum estimate of total subsistence salmon harvest in the study area was 49,530 (95% confidence limits [CL]: 44,175–55,147) during 17 fishing opportunities with data collection between June 3 and August 10, 2024. Most salmon harvested were Chinook Salmon (21,492; 19,199–24,057), followed by Sockeye Salmon (*O. nerka*; 13,616; 95% CL: 11,337–16,323), Chum Salmon (12,911; 10,827–15,004), and Coho Salmon (1,511; 1,212–1,870). These estimates do not include harvests that (a) occurred in tributaries of the lower Kuskokwim River, (b) occurred downriver of the lower river boundary of Eek Island or upriver of Bogus Creek, (c) arose from non-gillnet capture methods, or (d) occurred during fishing opportunities on July 2, 8, 12, 13, 17, 19, and 23–31, and August 15 and 16. While the sampling and analytical methods remained standardized and generally consistent with previous years, harvest and effort estimation for the 2024 season, similar to 2022 and 2023, was facilitated by a customized software package (termed ‘KuskoHarvEst’) for program R that provides an intuitive, menu-driven workflow. This allowed the coauthors to independently execute the estimation model and confer on results. This software will be useful for future seasons in which inseason harvest and effort estimates are desired for the lower Kuskokwim River subsistence salmon fishery and during which similar fishing opportunities and sampling occurs.

Keywords: subsistence, inseason harvest, Kuskokwim River, Chinook, Chum, Sockeye, Coho

INTRODUCTION

Inseason management of Kuskokwim River salmon fisheries is undertaken in the face of a severe lack of information, due in a large part to the size and remoteness of the river system and limited funds to monitor inseason harvests. Fully-informed management would require continuous and accurate information on run timing, harvest, and escapement for each return year (Staton and Catalano 2019). With knowledge on these three components, it would be possible to know how much of the run is yet to come, how much escapement potential remains, and how many more fish may be harvested. Inseason management of Kuskokwim River salmon has historically been conducted with little of this information and has instead relied largely on a single and highly uncertain index (the Bethel Test Fishery¹ [BTF]) of run abundance, run timing, and species composition to inform decision-making. Western science has developed methods to obtain more detailed information on run timing (Staton et al. 2017) and relative run size (e.g., a recent mainstem sonar project², and a Bayesian approach to update run size forecasts with inseason data on a daily basis; Staton and Catalano 2019), and to deliver this information to managers and stakeholders in a timely manner for decision-making. Local and Indigenous Knowledge shared by Kuskokwim River harvesters and Tribal inseason managers during Federal-Tribal and public management meetings provides additional information on salmon return strength and timing. Based on observations of non-salmon species migrations, weather patterns, year-round climate, run timing information, and other natural indicators, this Local and Indigenous Knowledge works alongside Western scientific tools used to predict salmon run characteristics.

However, even with perfect holistic information on these run characteristics, the number of fish harvested drainage-wide inseason is unknown, despite its critical importance for structuring inseason fishing opportunities and ensuring adequate salmon escapement. Some harvest data have been collected from the Bethel area by the Orutsararmiut Native Council (ONC) since the 1980s (A. Nadine Rogers, ONC, per, com.), although inseason harvest estimates were not produced. Timely inseason subsistence harvest estimates have only been available relatively recently in the Kuskokwim River (2016–2023) to inform inseason management and remain a critical information source necessary to successfully manage weak salmon runs. This report follows previous documentation of inseason salmon harvest estimates from short-duration Kuskokwim River subsistence fishing opportunities to estimate inseason harvest during the 2024 season (Staton and Coggins 2016, 2017; Staton 2018; Decossas 2019a, 2020; Russell et al. 2021; Bechtol and Schomogyi 2022; Bechtol et al. 2024).

In response to multi-year conservation concerns for the Kuskokwim River Chinook Salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*) season (Larson 2024), and expectations of weak Chum Salmon (*O. keta*) and Coho Salmon (*O. kisutch*) returns in 2024, the Refuge Manager of the Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge (YDNWR), through action by the Federal Subsistence Board, assumed primary management authority of Kuskokwim River subsistence salmon fisheries within the boundaries of the YDNWR on June 1, 2024 (Figure 1; [Temporary Special Action No: FSA-YD-24-01](#)). This area is also commonly referred to as federal waters of the Kuskokwim River or the lower Kuskokwim River.

¹ <https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/index.cfm?adfg=commercialbyareakuskokwim.btf>

² <https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/index.cfm?adfg=commercialbyareakuskokwim.emihd>

The Refuge Manager, in consultation with the Kuskokwim River Inter-Tribal Fish Commission (KRITFC) Tribal In-Season Managers as YDNWR’s collaborative management partners, decided that the use of restricted fishing time, area closures, and gear restrictions would provide adequate measures to manage the fishery. The restricted fishing time, or “block openings,” provided focused harvest opportunities with closed periods between openings to allow some Chinook, Chum, and Coho salmon to pass through areas of high fishing effort, thereby protecting significant amounts of returning salmon for spawner escapement and also for harvesters residing above YDNWR boundaries. Block openings also established specific windows to gather data for inseason harvest estimation and gave decisionmakers time in between openings to consider potential future fishing opportunities. Additionally, both the Refuge Manager and KRITFC managers agreed that several block opening fishing opportunities should be announced prior to the beginning of the Chinook Salmon season so people could plan for fishing, which provides greater certainty for subsistence harvesters and reduces complexity of inseason management. The Refuge Manager and KRITFC also agreed that 6-inch set gillnet opportunities should be provided to Federally-Qualified Subsistence Users in order to provide a “taste of salmon” during June 3 to June 10³.

On May 21, 2024, the Refuge Manager published Temporary Special Action (TSA) No: FSA-YD-24-01⁴. The issuance of a TSA differs from the Emergency Special Actions (ESAs) issued in previous years in that a TSA may be applied for a longer time frame, up to 90 days, an aspect that was warranted given the low Coho Salmon return in 2022 and the potential need for conservation measures later in the 2024 summer. Effective June 1, 2024, FSA-YD-24-01⁴ announced that unless reopened by the YDNWR Refuge Manager, fishing for salmon with gillnets was closed in the following Federal public waters of the Kuskokwim River within and adjacent to the exterior boundaries of the YDNWR; (1) the Kuskokwim River mainstem within YDNWR boundaries; (2) the Eek, Kwethluk, Kasigluk, Kisaralik, Tuluksak, and Aniak rivers, and the Aniak Box, with rivers not listed restricted to fishing at least 100 yards upriver from the confluence with the Kuskokwim River mainstem. However, Federally Qualified Subsistence Users fishing with dip nets, beach seines, fish wheels, and rod and reel were permitted to retain Chinook, Chum, Coho, and Sockeye salmon in all YDNWR waters. The Refuge Manager subsequently announced the fishing opportunities shown below. The approach of announcing a limited number of fisheries openings was intended to provide subsistence harvest opportunities without risking Chinook and Chum salmon escapement until additional data became available. Because of conservation concerns for salmon populations, these subsistence opportunities were limited to Federally Qualified Subsistence Users, which include all residents of the Kuskokwim River drainage per regulations written in Title VIII of the Alaska National Interest Lands Conservation Act (ANILCA).

The Refuge Manager expected relatively few Chinook and Chum salmon would be harvested during the early opportunities based on past low numbers of salmon in the river during the front-end closure, plus the net length and operational restrictions for set gillnets during this time. Estimates were not produced for harvests from non-gillnet methods, from non-spawning tributaries, downstream of YDNWR boundaries, or upstream of area D2 (Figure 1). These

³<https://www.kuskosalmon.org/news/earlyjune-fishing2024>

⁴ <https://www.kuskosalmon.org/news/2024tsa>

harvest areas were excluded because aerial surveys do not monitor these areas, interview data coverage was limited, and harvests were generally thought to be small relative to mainstem harvests with gillnets.

There were 17 subsistence fishery opportunities announced for June 3 to August 16, 2024, in the YDNWR boundaries³:

1. 6/3/24 07:00 am – 11:00 pm; 16 hours; set gillnet only
2. 6/6/24 07:00 am – 11:00 pm; 16 hours; set gillnet only
3. 6/10/24 07:00 am – 11:00 pm; 16 hours; set gillnet only
4. 6/12/24 07:00 am – 07:00 pm; 12 hours; drift or set gillnet
5. 6/16/24 07:00 am – 07:00 pm; 12 hours drift or set gillnet
6. 6/22/2024 07:00 am – 07:00 pm; 12 hours drift or set gillnet
7. 7/1/24 12:00 pm – 7/2/24 12:00 pm; 24 hours; set gillnet only
8. 7/6/24 12:00 pm – 7/8/24 12:00 pm; 48 hours; set gillnet only
9. 7/12/24 12:00 pm – 7/13/24 12:00 pm; 24 hours; drift or set gillnet
10. 7/16/24 12:00 pm – 7/17/24 12:00 pm; 24 hours; set gillnet only
11. 7/19/24 12:00 pm – 7/20/24 12:00 pm; 24 hours; drift or set gillnet
12. 7/23/24 12:00 pm – 7/24/24 12:00 pm; 24 hours; set gillnet only
13. 7/26/24 12:00 pm – 7/27/24 12:00 pm; 24 hours; drift or set gillnet
14. 7/23/24 06:00 am – 7/31/24 11:59 pm; 9 days; drift or set gillnet
15. 8/5/24 09:00 am – 09:00 pm; 12 hours; drift or set gillnet
16. 8/10/24 09:00 am – 09:00 pm; 12 hours; drift or set gillnet
17. 8/15/24 11:59 am – 8/16/24 11:59 pm; 36 hours; drift or set gillnet

Federal restrictions to the harvest of salmon were rescinded on August 17, 2024, per the Refuge Manager’s [FSA-YD-24-02](#)⁵.

METHODS

The inseason harvest estimation framework that was developed and applied to the 2016–2024 Kuskokwim River salmon seasons required two primary types of information: (1) an estimate of the total number of fishing trips each day (termed “effort”); and (2) completed trip interview data from subsistence harvesters to document fishing trip gear and catch characteristics, including: total trip time, net-in-water time, general fishing location, gillnet length and mesh size, and catch by species (Staton and Coggins 2016, 2017; Staton 2018; Decossas 2019, 2020; Russell et al. 2021; Bechtol and Schomogyi 2022; Bechtol et al. 2024). For a complete description of analytical and sampling methods, see Staton (2018) and Staton et al. (2025).

⁵ <https://www.doi.gov/media/document/notice-rescind-salmon-fishing-restrictions-within-federal-waters-kuskokwim-river>

Aerial Net Counts

For each harvest opportunity or block opening (duration of 12 to 48 hours depending on date and legal gear), USFWS attempted to conduct one to two flights between the river mouth by Eek Island and Bogus Creek near the community of Tuluksak, depending on factors such as expected effort, weather, and budget considerations (Tables 1 and 2; Figure 1). Based on YDNWR staff and USFWS pilot availability, some flights were also conducted with KRITFC observers and also on flights chartered by KRITFC. Flights were scheduled to document net counts between low and high tides when the tides were moving the strongest (which are the most popular times to fish), and flights were spaced across openings. Individual flights lasted around 1½ to 2½ hours (Tables 1 and 2). The analytical method for converting aerial counts to estimates of total effort includes estimates of trips that were likely to have been counted on multiple flights, and trips that were unlikely to have been counted on any flight, as is described in Staton (2018). Net counts upriver from Bethel are treated as the maximum observed between upriver and downriver flights. Based on input from the YDNWR staff, the approach beginning in 2022 has been to sum set gillnet counts on flight legs below Bethel because many set gillnet locations are only visible on either the downriver or upriver passes (Bechtol and Schomogyi 2022; A. Moses, USFWS, pers. com.).

Completed Trip Interviews

Information from harvester trips was obtained from three sources in 2024: (1) the Bethel boat harbor, (2) Bethel area fish camps, and (3) eight lower Kuskokwim River villages other than Bethel. Interview data from sources (1) and (2) were collected by ONC using methods similar to those used since 1988 (A. Nadine Rogers, ONC, per. com.), although YDNWR and KRITFC staff also helped conduct the interviews at the Bethel Boat Harbor beginning in mid-July in 2024. Data from lower Kuskokwim River villages other than Bethel were collected by KRITFC community harvest monitors with the same methods adopted in 2017 as part of a community-based harvest monitoring (CBM; also referred to as CBHM) project designed to provide interview data from areas of the YDNWR other than the Bethel area. In 2024, a total of 17 KRITFC community harvest monitors were located in the villages of Eek, Tuntutuliak, Napakiak, Napaskiak, Kwethluk, Akiachak, Akiak, and Tuluksak.

Staffs from KRITFC, ONC, USFWS, and the Alaska Department of Fish and Game met in person or virtually on April 12 and 17, 2024, to discuss the inseason harvest estimation project. These staffs then met with ONC and KRITFC interviewers in Bethel on May 30, 2024, for a day of training on interview techniques, including Principles for Conducting Research in the Arctic⁶, and collection of age, sex, and length (ASL) samples.

During the 2024 season, data from all sources were generally compiled in a timely manner (by 12 to 36 hours following an opening) to be included in a harvest estimate summary provided to inseason managers and a broader distribution that includes agency staffs and any interested public. However, interview data for a small number of cases were received too late for inclusion in the inseason harvest reports. These interview data are included in this final report and had

⁶ <https://www.iarpccollaborations.org/principles.html>

little effect on harvest estimates by date, but note that catch and effort estimates on an individual date in this report may differ slightly from harvest estimates produced inseason. In total, 1,193 inseason harvest interviews were conducted among the three sources: 575 (48%) from the Bethel boat harbor as sampled by ONC, KRITFC, and USFWS; 559 (47%) from KRITFC community-based harvest monitors; and 59 (5%) from fish camps sampled by ONC.

Analytical Methods

Analytical methods in 2024 were similar to previous years as described in Staton (2018) and Staton et al. (2025) except for: (1) extension of the area included to stratum D2 in 2023 and 2024 (Figure 1) based on expanded aerial flight coverage and interviews from Tuluksak; (2) inclusion of Coho Salmon harvest data in the assessment in 2023 and 2024 due to concerns over poor Coho Salmon returns in recent years; and (3) extension of the harvest estimation period into August to better identify Coho Salmon harvests. Note that some interviews were available from fishing efforts in reporting strata O (i.e., downriver of the YDNWR boundary or in non-spawning tributaries) and in strata D3 (Figure 1), but are not included in these harvest estimates because there was no aerial survey coverage for these areas.

Harvest estimates were made through a custom software package for program R entitled ‘KuskoHarvEst’ (Staton 2021). ‘KuskoHarvEst’ aims to: (1) facilitate installation of software needed to perform estimation and generate reports; (2) remove software editing needed for each harvest opportunity; and (3) enforce consistency and remove subjectivity in data quality checking and censoring. The package accomplishes these tasks by being self-contained, easily downloadable, and providing an intuitive menu-driven workflow for all data processing and estimation steps. Routines in the R package are automated for conducting calculations developed in the 2016–2018 seasons (Staton and Coggins 2016, 2017; Staton 2018). Following the conclusion of the 2021 season, software development has continued based on feedback from the 2021 experience with the first version, largely to improve the ability to detect and handle data formatting issues (B. Staton, Quantitative Ecological Services, pers. com.). Note that the software as currently configured does not accommodate interviews from harvesters that fished across multiple days (i.e., for a fishing trip that started on one day and ended on the subsequent day). In cases for which fishing trips spanned more than a single day, reported harvest was apportioned between adjacent days according to hours of the fishing trip reported for those adjacent days. Due to weather or staffing issues, an insufficient number of interviews, or anticipated low effort, harvest estimates were not made for the July 2, 8, 12, 13, 17, 19, and 23–31, or August 15–16 fishing days in 2024.

Minor edits to the harvest estimation program continued in 2024 as issues were resolved (e.g., under certain instances of low effort, the estimated drift gillnet harvest exceeded the total drift plus set gillnet estimate). Coauthors reviewed the updated software prior to the 2024 season and had the opportunity to independently use the software inseason to produce the estimates for each harvest opportunity. Results were consistent among coauthors, with the biggest issue being data formatting errors that were often, but not always, identified by the interface computer code.

Note that harvest estimate totals across species or across strata may differ slightly from the total sums of individual estimated catches as shown in the tables due to small rounding differences.

RESULTS

6/3/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

An estimated total of 78 set gillnet trips occurred in the study area during the 16-hour opening on June 3 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 53 (95% CL: 21–91). Most (94%) of the harvested salmon were Chinook Salmon (50; 95% CL: 21–81), followed by Chum Salmon at 6% of the harvest (4; 95% CL: 0–13), with no other salmon caught (Tables 4 and 6; Figure 4). Harvest estimates were produced from 24 trip interviews, of which 19 (79%) came from community harvest monitors, 5 (21%) from the Bethel boat harbor, and 0 (0%) from the ONC area fish camps (Figure 5). For the June 3 opening, trip duration averaged 9.5 hours, and soak time averaged 9.0 hours among interviews (Figure 6).

6/6/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

An estimated total of 156 setnet trips occurred in the study area during the 16-hour opening on June 6 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 451 (95% CL: 278–637). Around 93% of the salmon harvest was Chinook Salmon (422; 95% CL: 255–606), followed by Sockeye Salmon at 5% (22; 95% CL: 0–68), and Chum Salmon at 2% (8; 95% CL: 0–25) (Tables 4 and 6; Figure 4). Harvest estimates were produced from 56 trip interviews, of which 31 (55%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, and 25 (45%) from community harvest monitors (Figure 5). For the June 6 opening, trip duration averaged 8.4 hours, and soak time averaged 8.1 hours among interviews (Figure 7).

6/10/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

An estimated total of 214 setnet trips occurred in the study area during the 16-hour opening on June 10 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 757 (95% CL: 516–1,039). Most (82%) of the harvest was Chinook Salmon (622; 95% CL: 413–869), followed by Chum Salmon at 11% (85; 95% CL: 30–147), and Sockeye Salmon at 7% (51; 95% CL: 17–95) (Tables 4 and 6; Figure 4). Harvest estimates were produced from 60 trip interviews, of which 32 (53%) came from community harvest monitors, and 28 (47%) from the Bethel boat harbor (Figure 5). For the June 10 opening, trip duration averaged 8.8 hours and soak time averaged 7.9 hours among interviews (Figure 8).

6/12/24 Opening (Drift and Set Gillnet)

An estimated total of 461 drift boat trips and 24 setnet trips occurred in the study area during the 12-hour opening on June 12 (Table 3; Figures 2 and 3). The estimated total salmon harvest was 4,158 (95% CL: 3,242–5,267). The majority of the harvest (81%) was Chinook Salmon (3,351; 95% CL: 2,609–4,270), followed by Chum Salmon at 15% (618; 95% CL: 332–977) and Sockeye Salmon at 4% (189; 95% CL: 108–295) (Tables 4–6; Figure 4). Harvest estimates were produced from 227 trip interviews, of which 132 (58%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, 76 (34%) from community harvest monitors, and 19 (8%) from Bethel area fish camps (Figure 5). Setnet harvesters provided 24 interviews with the remaining 203 interviews from driftnet users.

Based on the distribution of interview quantities for driftnets from the June 12 opening (Figure 9), trip duration averaged 6.9 hours and soak time averaged 4.9 hours. Salmon catch per driftnet trip during the June 12 opening averaged 4.1 for Chinook, 0.5 for Chum, and 0.4 for Sockeye salmon (Figure 9). As in recent years, the average harvesters interviewed by community harvest monitors spent more time fishing and had higher catches/trip than reported at Bethel area fish camps or the Bethel boat harbor.

6/16/24 Opening (Drift and Set Gillnet)

An estimated total of 505 drift boat trips and 85 setnet trips occurred within the study area during the 12-hour opening on June 16 (Table 3; Figures 2 and 3). The estimated total salmon harvest was 8,938 (95% CL: 7,584–10,779). A majority (74%) of the harvest was Chinook Salmon (6,561; 95% CL: 5,374–8,126), followed by Sockeye Salmon at 16% of the harvest (1,454; 95% CL: 1,052–1,887), and Chum Salmon at 10% of the harvest (923; 95% CL: 710–1,176) (Tables 4–6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 213 completed trip interviews, of which 115 (54%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, 78 (37%) came from community harvest monitors, and 20 (9%) came from Bethel area fish camps (Figure 5). Of these interviews, 7 (3%) were from setnet harvesters and 206 (97%) were from driftnet harvesters.

Based on the distribution of relevant driftnet interview quantities from this opening (Figure 10), trip durations (average 7.3 hours) and soak durations (average 5.7 hours) were higher than the June 12 opening. Salmon catch per driftnet trip increased substantially over the June 12 opening for Chinook (average 9.9), Chum (average 1.8), and Sockeye (average 1.7) salmon (Figures 9 and 10).

6/22/24 Opening (Drift and Set Gillnet)

An estimated total of 475 drift boat trips and 39 setnet trips occurred in the study area during the 12-hour opening on June 22 (Table 3; Figures 2 and 3). The estimated total salmon harvest was 24,319 (95% CL: 19,584–29,504). Chinook Salmon were the most numerous fish harvested at 36% of the harvest (8,709; 95% CL: 6,841–10,651). Sockeye Salmon comprised 33% of the

salmon harvest (7,953; 95% CL: 5,831–10,571), followed by Chum Salmon at 31% of the harvest (7,657; 95% CL: 5,826–9,604) (Tables 4–6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 213 trip interviews, of which 110 (52%) came from community harvest monitors, 92 (43%) from the Bethel boat harbor, and 11 (5%) from Bethel area fish camps (Figure 5). Driftnet users provided 206 interviews, with 7 interviews from setnet harvesters.

Based on the distribution of relevant drift harvester interview quantities from this opening, trip duration among harvesters averaged 6.6 hours, and soak time averaged 4.5 hours (Figure 11). Catches rates per trip for driftnet boats averaged 11.4 for Chinook, 9.0 for Sockeye, and 8.2 for Chum salmon. Harvesters interviewed by community harvest monitors and at Bethel area fish camps on average had longer fishing trips and higher soak times and catch rates than people interviewed at the Bethel boat harbor.

7/1/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

Data were only available for July 1 from the 24-hour opening. An estimated total of 148 setnet trips occurred in the study area on July 1 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 4,700 (95% CL: 3,650–5,811). The largest component (44%) of the harvest was Sockeye Salmon (2,078; 95% CL: 1,568–2,640), followed by 36% Chum Salmon (1,700; 95% CL: 1,127–2,305), and 20% Chinook Salmon (921; 95% CL: 657–1,277) (Tables 4 and 6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 73 trip interviews, of which 67 (92%) came from KRITFC community harvest monitors 6 (8%) from the Bethel boat harbor (Figure 5).

Setnet trip duration averaged 7.9 hours and soak times averaged 7.3 hours, with setnet catches rates averaging 11.6 per trip for Sockeye, 6.8 for Chum, and 4.4 for Chinook salmon (Figure 12). Trip duration, soak times, and average catch/trip for all salmon species were greatest for community harvest monitors.

7/6/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

Data presented here represent noon to midnight on July 6 from a 48-hour opening that began on July 6. An estimated total of 68 setnet trips occurred in the study area on July 6 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 2,145 (95% CL: 1,581–2,732). The largest component (43%) of the harvest was Sockeye Salmon (920; 95% CL: 680–1,212), followed by 32% Chum Salmon (683; 95% CL: 403–963), and 25% Chinook Salmon (542; 95% CL: 285–786) (Tables 4 and 6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 25 setnet trip interviews, of which 18 (72%) came from community harvest monitors and 5 (20%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, and 2 (8%) from Bethel area fish camps (Figure 5). Setnet trip duration averaged 7.3 hours and soak time averaged 7.2 hours (Figure 13). While trip duration and soak times were highest for Bethel area

fish camps, catches/trip for Chinook, Chum, and Sockeye salmon were highest for interviews by community harvest monitors.

7/7/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

Data presented here represent midnight to midnight on July 7 from a 48-hour opening that began on July 6. An estimated total of 46 setnet trips occurred in the study area on July 7 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 1,887 (95% CL: 1,372–2,443). The largest component (57%) of the harvest was Sockeye Salmon (1,081; 95% CL: 711–1,472), followed by 29% Chum Salmon (542; 95% CL: 327–859), and 14% Chinook Salmon (264; 95% CL: 151–393) (Tables 4 and 6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 46 setnet trip interviews, of which 25 (54%) came from community harvest monitors and 18 (39%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, and 3 (7%) from Bethel area fish camps (Figure 5). Setnet trip duration averaged 6.5 hours and soak time averaged 6.1 hours (Figure 14). Trip duration, soak times, and Chum, and Sockeye salmon catch/trip were highest for Bethel area fish camps, with Chinook Salmon catch/trip highest for community harvest monitors.

7/16/24 Opening (Set Gillnet Only)

An estimated total of 18 setnet trips occurred in the study area during the 24-hour set gillnet opening that began on July 16; data are only presented for noon to midnight on July 16 (Table 3; Figures 2 and 3). Estimated total salmon harvest was 442 (95% CL: 195–752). The majority (52%) of the harvest was Sockeye Salmon (228; 95% CL: 105–378), followed by 29% Chum Salmon (129; 95% CL: 72–188), 10% Chinook Salmon (46; 95% CL: 7–105), and 9% Coho Salmon (39; 95% CL: 0–102) (Table 6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 15 setnet trip interviews, of which 14 (93%) came from community harvest monitors, and 1 (7%) from the Bethel boat harbor (Figure 5). Trip duration averaged 6.3 hours and soak time averaged 6.0 hours (Figure 15).

7/20/24 Opening (Drift and Set Gillnet)

An estimated total of 8 drift and 7 set gillnet trips occurred in the study area during midnight to noon on July 20 as part of a 24-hour set gillnet opening that began at noon on July 19; no estimates were available for July 19 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 342 (95% CL: 225–439). The majority (56%) of the harvest was Chum Salmon (190; 95% CL: 135–243), followed by 37% Sockeye Salmon (127; 95% CL: 63–180), 3% Chinook Salmon (12; 95% CL: 0–31), and 4% Coho Salmon (13; 95% CL: 0–24) (Tables 4–6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 14 trip interviews, of which 10 (71%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, and 4 (29%) from community harvest monitors (Figure 5). Driftnet trip

duration averaged 1.9 hours and soak time averaged 1.4 hours (Figure 16), with both measures being substantial decreases from previous openings.

As a caveat, harvest data were successfully generated for July 20 alone, but issues emerged when producing a season total because of how data are “borrowed” across multiple adjacent strata with low sample sizes. Catch and effort estimates for July 20 are provided here for documentation purposes, but the total inseason harvest estimates exclude the July 20 data.

8/5/24 Opening (Drift and Set Gillnet)

An estimated total of 48 drift and 11 set gillnet trips occurred in the study area during the 12-hour opening on August 5 (Table 3; Figure 2). The estimated total salmon harvest was 1,493 (95% CL: 1,273–1,733). The majority (86%) of the harvest was Coho Salmon (1,291; 95% CL: 1,078–1,509), followed by 8% Sockeye Salmon (115; 95% CL: 80–156), 6% Chum Salmon (87; 95% CL: 49–129), and <1% Chinook Salmon (1; 95% CL: 0–2) (Tables 4–6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 48 trip interviews, of which 37 (77%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, and 11 (23%) from community harvest monitors (Figure 5). Drift gillnet catch/trip was highest for the Bethel Boat Harbor for Coho and Chum salmon, and highest for community harvest monitors for Sockeye and Chinook salmon. Driftnet trip duration averaged 4.0 hours and was highest for community harvest monitors (9.0 hours), than for the Bethel Boat Harbor (3.5 hours), but soak duration was higher for the Bethel Boat Harbor (2.3 hours) than for community harvest monitors (1.4 hours; Figure 17).

As a caveat and similar to July 20, harvest data were successfully generated for August 5 alone, but issues emerged when producing a season total because of how data are “borrowed” across multiple adjacent strata with low sample sizes. Catch and effort estimates for August 5 are provided here for documentation purposes, but the total inseason harvest estimates exclude the August 5 data.

8/10/24 Opening (Drift and Set Gillnet)

An estimated total of 51 driftnet trips and 6 setnet trips occurred in the study area during the 12-hour drift and set gillnet opening on August 10 (Table 3; Figures 2 and 3). The estimated total salmon harvest was 1,680 (95% CL: 1,388–2,016). The majority (88%) of the harvest was Coho Salmon (1,472; 95% CL: 1,162–1,826), followed by 10% Sockeye Salmon (172; 95% CL: 62–346), 2% Chum Salmon (31; 95% CL: 14–54), and <1% Chinook Salmon (4; 95% CL: 0–10) (Table 6; Figure 4).

Harvest estimates were produced from 56 trip interviews, of which 36 (64%) came from the Bethel boat harbor, and 18 (32%) from community harvest monitors, and 2 (4%) from Bethel area fish camps (Figure 5). Catch/trip for Coho Salmon was highest for the Bethel Boat Harbor, and highest for Chum Salmon for community harvest monitors. Driftnet trip duration averaged 4.1 hours and soak time averaged 2.8 hours (Figure 18).

Total Harvest across Openings

Insufficient or no data were available to make harvest estimates for July 2, 8, 12, 13, 17, 19, and 23–31, or August 15 and 16. In addition, 25 interviews of harvesters fishing stratum O (primarily non-spawning tributaries and below Eek Island) and above Bogus Creek (above stratum D2) had no corresponding aerial survey counts of nets (Figure 1). Because interview data were not expanded to total estimates for these unsurveyed areas, the total harvests reported here should be regarded as underestimates.

The need to exclude the July 20 and August 5 harvest data from the season total is a concern, especially since the August 5 harvest would have accounted for nearly half of the total Coho Salmon harvest during the 2024 inseason harvest reporting season. A stratum with a sample size too low for analysis is categorized as NA, but a daily total harvest by species and across stratum is estimated, excluding the NA data. However, the existing computer code excludes days on which NA designations exist, which resulted in incorrect data summaries for the 2024 season tied to NA values on July 20 and August 5. Resolving this issue is something being explored prior to the 2025 season.

Across all openings, an estimated total of 49,530 (95% CL: 44,175–55,147) salmon was harvested (Table 6; Figure 19). This estimate does not include harvests that (a) occurred in tributaries of the lower Kuskokwim River; (b) occurred above Bogus Creek; (c) were from non-gillnet capture methods; or (d) occurred during fishing opportunities on dates other than those described above and for which no or insufficient data were available to make harvest estimates. This total 2024 harvest was 25% less than the average annual harvest of all salmon from 2016–2023 (Table 7). Within the study area, the largest contributor to the 2024 total salmon catch (40%) was stratum C (20,038 salmon; 95% CL: 17,758–22,769), the area surrounding Bethel (Table 6; Figure 1). Salmon catch contributions from other strata were 33% from stratum A (16,307 salmon; 95% CL: 12,351–20,802), 13% stratum B (6,462 salmon; 95% CL: 5,397–7,720), 7% stratum D1 (3,375 salmon; 85% CL: 2,870–3,883), and 7% stratum D2 (3,449 salmon; 95% CL: 2,796–3,940).

Chinook Salmon was the largest contributor (43% of the total) to the 2024 inseason harvest estimate with a total of 21,492 fish (95% CL: 19,199–24,057; Table 6; Figure 19). Stratum C produced 37% of the Chinook Salmon harvest, followed by 34% from A, 15% from B, 8% from D1, and 6% from D2 (Figure 20). The 2024 harvest of Chinook Salmon was the third lowest since 2016 and 11% lower than the average harvest during 2016–2023 (Table 7).

The harvest of 13,616 Sockeye Salmon (95% CL: 11,337–16,323) comprised 28% of the total 2024 inseason salmon harvest estimate (Table 6; Figure 20). Stratum C produced 49% of the Sockeye Salmon harvest, followed by 24% from A, 14% from B, 7% from D2, and 6% from D1 (Figure 20). The 2024 Sockeye Salmon harvest was 36% less than the 2016–2023 average harvest (Table 7).

The total inseason estimate of 12,911 (95% CL: 10,953–15,278) Chum Salmon harvested in 2024 comprised 26% of the estimate for all salmon (Table 16; Figure 20). This continued an increase in inseason harvest estimates of Chum Salmon since 2019, but was still 35% less than

the average harvest during 2016–2023 (Table 7). Stratum A produced 43% of the Chum Salmon harvest, followed by 33% from C, 11% from B, 8% from D2, and 5% from D1 (Figure 20).

The harvest of 1,511 Coho Salmon (95% CL: 1,212–1,870) comprised 3% of the total 2024 inseason salmon harvest estimate (Table 6; Figure 20). Stratum C produced 81% of the Coho Salmon harvest, followed by 11% from D1, 5% from D2, 2% from B, and 1% from A (Figure 20). Because this was only the 2nd year to estimate inseason harvests of Coho Salmon, other years were not considered for comparison (Table 7). Because these values exclude catches on July 20 and August 5, they should be considered underestimates. But also note that the 2024 inseason estimates include harvests from stratum D2 (Akiak to Bogus Creek), which was first included in 2023 data.

In 2024, maximum driftnet effort occurred on June 16 and maximum setnet effort occurred on June 10 (Table 3).

Summary of Key Information on 6/12 Openings

June 12 is a key opening date, following June 1 to June 11 restrictions to allow early returning Chinook Salmon to migrate upstream (Smith and Gray 2022). Table 8 shows information on the 12-hour openings that have been implemented on June 12 from 2016 to 2024. These data only cover strata A to D1 because D2 was first included in 2023. There are several notable findings from June 12 fishing opportunities during 2016–2024. The number of driftnet and setnet trips from Eek to just above Akiak peaked at 584 trips in 2017, and the 459 trips in 2024 was essentially the same as the long-term average during 2016–2023 (Table 8).

In terms of total harvest, this first combined 12-hour drift and set gillnet opening in 2024 resulted in an estimated total harvest of 4,009 salmon (excluding stratum D2), more than in 2023 but 23% less than the average June 12 harvest during 2016–2024 (Table 8). The estimated harvests of 3,222 Chinook Salmon and 602 chum salmon were also higher than in 2023, although the Chinook catch was 22% less and the chum harvest 17% less than the long-term average for June 12. In contrast, 2024 the harvest of 185 Sockeye Salmon was the second lowest for June 12 since 2016 and 48% less than the 2016–2023 average. The species ratio (Chum+Sockeye/Chinook) of 0.24 in 2024 was 33% less than the long-term average (Table 8).

DISCUSSION

Overall Summary

For the 2024 season, an inseason estimated total of 50,880 (95% CL: 45,203–56,759) salmon was harvested in strata A to D2 (Figure 1; Tables 6 and 8). This estimate was 11% less than the average during 2016–2023, the years for which the current inseason harvest estimation program has been implemented. The largest catch component (42%) in 2024 was the harvest of 21,500 Chinook Salmon (95% CL: 19,201–24,059), representing an 11% decline from the 2016–2023

average annual harvest. Sockeye Salmon was the second largest contributor (27%) to the 2024 inseason harvest estimate with a total of 13,780 fish (95% CL: 11,484–16,534), representing a 35% decline from the 2016–2023 average. The 2024 harvest of 13,090 Chum Salmon (95% CL: 10,953–15,278) comprised 26% of the 2024 inseason harvest estimate, but was 34% less than the 2016–2023 average harvest. The harvest of 2,510 Coho Salmon (95% CL: 1,305–3,232) was 5% of the total 2024 inseason salmon harvest estimate; 2024 was only the second year that Coho Salmon have been included in the inseason harvest estimates.

As noted previously, the 2024 estimates do not include harvests: from July 2, 8, 12, 13, 17, 19, and 23–31, and August 15 and 16; from non-salmon spawning tributaries; from areas outside the YDNWR boundaries; or from areas upriver of Bogus Creek (Figure 1). Reasons for excluding data for certain dates are typically related to: (1) a lack of aerial surveys to count nets; or (2) an insufficient number of interviews. In total, 1,193 inseason harvest interviews were conducted among the three sources: 575 (48%) from the Bethel boat harbor as sampled by ONC, KRITFC, and USFWS; 559 (47%) from KRITFC community-based harvest monitors; and 59 (5%) from Bethel area fish camps sampled by ONC.

For set gillnets fished over midnight between days (e.g., noon on July 6 to noon on July 7), it was necessary to divide the catch across days for accommodation by the harvest estimation code. This likely resulted in an overestimation of the number of nets fished across multi-day openings, although the total catch estimate should still be fairly accurate. If one of the days over which the catch is divided is excluded from consideration due to one of the reasons listed above, the estimate is only made for the day with adequate data. Revision of the estimation code to consider fishing across multiple days is a future consideration.

Note that the 2024 fishing season differed from 2016–2023 in several aspects. For one, the period of federal fishery management on the Lower Kuskokwim River extended from June 1 to August 16, a longer period than most previous years. The original assumption of fishery management by USFWS under the provisions of ANILCA Title VIII was tied to a dramatic decline of Chinook Salmon stocks returning to the Kuskokwim River after a record low return in 2012. That decline was followed in recent years by an equally dramatic decline in Chum Salmon stocks. Then, following poor Coho Salmon runs with a record low return in 2022, concerns emerged over the potential status of Coho Salmon in 2023 and 2024 and federal management continued until mid-August, when it became apparent that the Coho Salmon return was stronger than observed in 2022 and stronger than projected for 2023. The 2023 inseason management program continued through the period of federal management to provide fishery managers with inseason harvest information into the early portion of the Coho Salmon return. However, management expectations were complicated due to the early curtailment of two major projects that assess salmon stock status on the Kuskokwim River: the Bethel Test Fishery and the Kuskokwim River Sonar.

A second difference for the 2023 and 2024 seasons was the revision to the harvest estimation computer code to allow inclusion of Coho Salmon (B. Staton, B. Staton, Quantitative Ecological Services, pers. com.). Harvests of Coho Salmon reported in interviews is now a selected option when estimating harvests.

Finally, the computer code was further modified to allow interviews and survey data from stratum D2 (Figure 1; B. Staton, Quantitative Ecological Services, pers. com.). Interview and aerial survey data were first available from stratum D2 in 2022, but it wasn't until 2023 that the computer code was modified to allow harvest estimation for stratum D2.

Given the above caveats, the estimates provided in this report should be considered minimum subsistence harvest estimates that will be revised through the Alaska Department of Fish and Game household surveys conducted postseason (e.g., Bembenic and Koster 2024).

It should also be noted that data presented in this report may differ slightly from harvest summaries provided inseason following individual openings. Substantial effort is made to receive the interview and flight data by about 12 hours after an opening, and process that data into a harvest estimate that can be distributed in 1-2 days after an opening. However, in several instances, and for a variety of reasons, interview data were not received until an initial harvest summary was distributed. These late data have been included in this report but did not have a substantial effect on harvest estimates, but did improve the precision of the estimates.

Reliability of Assumptions

All reported analyses assumed the interview information to be random samples from the population of harvesters during the openings (Bernard et al. 1998). This assumption is not unique to this analysis, or creel surveys in general, but is made in every statistical analysis where samples are used to make inferences on a population. We must highlight that sampling for the completed trip interviews was not implemented as truly random, but was opportunistic. The potential for non-randomness could raise questions about the harvest estimates in terms of accuracy and precision. If data were systematically biased (e.g., some people interviewed fished longer and had higher catch rates than non-sampled harvesters), then the resulting estimates would also be biased. While surveys had both high and low catches, we believe these estimates thoroughly represent the available harvest results and efforts. In addition, the software was recently revised to exclude interview data that exceeding three standard deviations from the mean (B. Staton, Quantitative Ecological Services, pers. com).

We believe the samples, although gathered opportunistically, provide a good representation of the lower Kuskokwim River subsistence fishery during block openings. Fishing opportunities in the 2024 season were relatively short in duration, ranging from 12 to 48 hours, aside from the 9-day opportunity in late-July during a period of low fishing effort between Chum and Coho salmon runs and during salmonberry-picking season. Overall, surveyor coverage at interview locations could sample a representation of harvesters returning to these locations, leading us to believe temporal representation was high (i.e., the samples should identify variability due to the time of day that different trips occurred). However, due to the size of the study area and the number of communities involved, spatial representation is more difficult to guarantee. The lower Kuskokwim River can be generally separated into three major sections based on river morphology, harvester behavior, and harvester density: (1) upriver from Bethel, (2) around Bethel, and (3) downriver from Bethel. A majority of the surveys collected were from around Bethel, primarily through the Bethel boat harbor surveys conducted by ONC, and later in the

season by KRITFC and USFWS. While most of the population of subsistence harvesters is based in and around Bethel, catch rates outside of Bethel can differ substantially from Bethel area harvests. For example, the villages of Napaskiak and Napakiak are relatively short boat rides (about 6 and 10 river miles, respectively) from Bethel, but exhibit different effort and harvest characteristics from Bethel.

Overall, interviews by ONC at the Bethel area fish camps, including at Oscarville and Napaskiak, and at the Bethel boat harbor by ONC, KRITFC, and USFWS provided a reasonable representation of the subsistence fishery in the Bethel area. Concurrently, KRITFC provided coverage through community-based harvest monitors based below Bethel in the villages of Eek, Tuntutuliak, Napakiak, and Napaskiak, and above Bethel in the villages of Kwethluk, Akiachak, Akiak, and Tuluksak. Given this broad geographic coverage within the study area, we believe data collected through the monitoring program are representative of the lower river subsistence fishery.

Other Harvest Not Monitored or Accounted For

Harvest estimates in this document for salmon within the study area are believed to be accurate for river areas represented by interviews and aerial net counts, but are undoubtedly biased low as an estimate for all of 2024. For example, gillnet harvests occurred in areas designated as “non-spawning tributaries” that were still part of the Kuskokwim River drainage. Harvest in these areas is poorly documented (Decossas 2019b). The 2024 interviews collected some information from subsistence users who fished in the non-salmon spawning tributaries (i.e., Johnson River, Tuntutuliak River, Gweek River, and Pailleq Slough). This aspect is further amplified because data from non-salmon spawning tributaries are often collected only when the mainstem fishery is open for fishing, but non-salmon spawning tributaries are open throughout the salmon season with fewer gear restrictions (e.g., gillnets with > 6” mesh are allowed), and some salmon do stray into and are caught in these non-salmon tributaries (Decossas 2019b). No data collected from non-salmon spawning tributaries were included in the 2024 harvest estimates. Harvest estimates were not generated for these locations, similar to previous years, because subsistence harvest interviews are generally collected only for announced fishing openings, and aerial surveys do not typically cover these areas. Similarly, harvest interviews were conducted with harvesters fishing just outside the YDNWR boundary near Eek Island and also from stratum D3, but these data are not included in the harvest estimates. While harvests in these locations are not believed to be detrimental to meeting escapement needs, the magnitude of salmon harvests in these locations remains unknown.

Additionally, Federally Qualified Subsistence Users were also able to harvest Chinook Salmon before June 1 with up to 6” mesh size gillnets. During this time period, harvest and effort are not monitored, although the number of Chinook Salmon in the Kuskokwim River is believed to have been minimal.

Subsistence harvests of salmon and other fish with non-gillnet gear in the main stem and non-spawning tributaries are also not accounted for in these in-season harvest estimates. These harvests include, but are not limited to, Sockeye Salmon caught with dipnets and Coho Salmon

caught with rod and reel, but Chinook and Chum salmon may also be caught with these gear types.

Finally, the coauthors would like to note that inseason harvest monitoring in 2024 encompassed the majority of the Chinook, Chum, and Sockeye salmon returns, but only the early portion of the Coho Salmon run. The extent to which inseason harvest during the Coho Salmon return is monitored in future years will likely depend on future trends of this stock.

Sensitivity of Harvest Estimates

Sensitivity of the estimates to assumption violations was investigated by producing effort and harvest estimates using data from smaller subsets of all of the available interviews (e.g., removing Bethel boat harbor interviews). Results of these analyses showed that the estimates were generally robust to leaving out information (i.e., making the information used presumably less representative), and the results ranged from small changes (<5%) in point estimates to larger changes (~15%). Typically, harvest estimates increased when Bethel boat harbor data were removed and decreased when the CBM interviews were removed. In most cases, the point estimate of the analysis with left-out data fell within the 95% CL of the original estimate and the qualitative conclusion did not change.

Again, one aspect that needs clarification is that some table values, if summed across date, location, or species, might not add up exactly to the displayed total. This is due to rounding of values and is an aspect considered for future resolution.

Technical Review of Harvest Estimates

During 2024, the harvest estimation model was run independently by two or more of the coauthors, or a coauthor and KRITFC staff, and the resulting estimates were resolved. Output differences were usually tied to data entry or formatting errors. After resolving data issues, harvest estimates were sent to an open email list that included USFWS-KRITFC inseason managers and researchers, the Kuskokwim River Salmon Management Working Group, Alaska Department of Fish and Game, and interested stakeholders.

Scalability of the Model

The current methods for estimating inseason salmon harvests are effective when applied to most fishery conditions that have occurred since 2016 (i.e., relatively few opportunities, each relatively short in duration). However, if the frequency and duration of fishing opportunities were to increase, a more carefully designed random sampling program may be needed to produce reliable harvest estimates. This is because longer openings make it more difficult to justify the assumption of random sampling at existing locations with interview coverage. Currently, interviewers are focused toward the end or just after the end of an opening. But as the duration of an opening increases, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate time and place to

conduct interviews to ensure interviews are a representative sample of the fishery. Interviews by phone have aided the interview process, but it is still uncertain how interviews might be randomized over a longer duration opening.

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Table 1. Raw set gillnet counts by geographic stratum for dates on which aerial net counts occurred, 2024.

Opening	Date	Flight Times ¹		Geographic Stratum ²					Total
		Start	Stop	A	B	C	D1	D2	
1	6/3/24	14:30	16:22	7	1	50	12	8	78
2	6/6/24	14:30	16:45	15	10	87	23	21	156
3	6/10/24	18:20	20:30	22	21	110	31	30	214
4	6/12/24	15:05	16:48	0	1	13	4	2	20
5	6/16/24	10:04	12:20	3	16	50	6	3	78
5	6/16/24	15:12	17:35	1	11	43	10	6	71
6	6/22/24	9:11	11:31	0	4	25	5	5	39
6	6/22/24	16:03	18:51	0	2	19	3	4	28
7	7/1/24	18:31	20:30	0	18	88	12	30	148
7	7/2/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
8	7/6/24	18:12	20:02	0	1	56	1	10	68
8	7/7/24	18:31	20:30	1	2	33	4	5	45
8	7/8/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
9	7/12/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
9	7/13/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
10	7/16/24	17:42	19:26	0	2	9	5	2	18
10	7/17/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
11	7/19/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
11	7/20/24	8:39	10:21	1	0	6	0	0	7
12	7/23/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
12	7/24/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
13	7/26/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
13	7/27/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
14	7/23-31/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
15	8/5/24	12:15	14:13	0	0	4	0	1	5
15	8/5/24	18:35	20:22	0	1	7	0	0	8
16	8/10/24	14:05	15:47	0	0	3	0	1	4
17	8/15/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
17	8/16/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

¹ND = No data

²Geographic strata: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, D2 = Akiak to Bogus Creek

Table 2. Raw drift gillnet counts by geographic stratum for dates on which aerial net counts occurred, 2024.

Opening	Date	Flight Times ¹		Geographic Stratum ²					Total
		Start	Stop	A	B	C	D1	D2	
1	6/3/24	14:30	16:22	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	6/6/24	14:30	16:45	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	6/10/24	18:20	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	6/12/24	15:05	16:48	102	34	109	24	15	284
5	6/16/24	10:04	12:20	136	70	186	36	21	449
5	6/16/24 ²	15:12	17:35	72	55	136	11	21	295
6	6/22/24	9:11	11:31	115	55	166	30	21	387
6	6/22/24	16:03	18:51	39	36	87	19	17	198
7	7/1/24	18:31	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	7/2/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
8	7/6/24	18:12	20:02	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	7/7/24	18:31	20:30	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	7/8/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
9	7/12/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
9	7/13/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
10	7/16/24	17:42	19:26	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	7/17/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
11	7/19/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
11	7/20/24	8:39	10:21	0	1	4	0	0	5
12	7/23/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
12	7/24/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
13	7/26/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
13	7/27/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
14	7/24-31/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
15	8/5/24	12:15	14:13	0	2	18	4	3	27
15	8/5/24	18:35	20:22	3	6	10	3	0	22
16	8/10/24	14:05	15:47	1	1	30	4	1	37
17	8/15/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
17	8/16/24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

¹ND = No data

²Geographic strata: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, D2 = Akiak to Bogus Creek

Table 3. Estimated drift and set gillnet trips by date and geographic stratum, 2024.
 These quantities were derived from the raw counts presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Gear	Opening	Date	Dura	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
				A	B	C	D1	D2	
Drift	1	6/3/24	16	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Gillnet	2	6/6/24	16	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	3	6/10/24	16	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	4	6/12/24	12	166	55	177	39	24	461
	5	6/16/24	12	138	86	221	30	30	505
	6	6/22/24	12	118	77	206	41	33	475
	7	7/1/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	7	7/2/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	8	7/6/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	8	7/7/24	24	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	8	7/8/23	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	9	7/12/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	9	7/13/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	10	7/16/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	10	7/17/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	11	7/19/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	11	7/20/24	12	0	2	6	0	0	8
	12	7/23/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	12	7/24/24	12	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	13	7/26/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	13	7/27/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	14	7/23– 31/24	9 days	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	15	8/5/24	12	3	8	27	7	3	48
	16	8/10/24	12	1	1	41	6	2	51
	17	8/15/24	24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	17	8/16/24	18	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

-continued-

Table 3 (Page 2 pf 2).

Gear	Opening	Date	Dura	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
				A	B	C	D1	D2	
Set	1	6/3/24	16	7	1	50	12	8	78
Gillnet	2	6/6/24	16	15	10	87	23	21	156
	3	6/10/24	16	22	21	110	31	30	214
	4	6/12/24	12	0	1	16	5	2	24
	5	6/16/24	12	2	16	53	9	5	85
	6	6/22/24	12	0	3	26	5	5	39
	7	7/1/24	12	9	18	88	12	30	148
	7	7/2/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	8	7/6/24	12	0	1	56	1	10	68
	8	7/7/24	24	1	2	34	4	5	46
	8	7/8/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	9	7/12/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	9	7/13/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	10	7/16/24	12	0	2	9	5	2	18
	10	7/17/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	11	7/19/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	11	7/20/24	12	1	0	6	0	0	7
	12	7/23/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
12	7/24/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
13	7/26/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
13	7/27/24	12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
14	7/23- 31/24	9 days	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
15	8/5/24	12	0	1	9	0	1	11	
16	8/10/24	12	0	0	4	0	2	6	
17	8/15/24	24	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
17	8/16/24	18	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	

¹Geographic strata: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, D2 – Akiak to Bogus Creek

²Duration is the number of hours in the opening.

NA = not applicable; e.g., drift gillnet closed on set-only opportunity

ND = No data or insufficient data,

Table 4. Salmon harvests from set gillnets by subsistence opening, species, and geographic stratum, 2024. Numbers within parentheses are 95% confidence limits.

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
6/3/24	Chinook	4 (2-7)	1 (0-1)	32 (14-52)	8 (3-13)	5 (2-8)	50 (21-81)
	Chum	0 (0-1)	0 (0-0)	3 (0-9)	1 (0-2)	0 (0-1)	4 (0-13)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	5 (2-8)	1 (0-1)	34 (14-59)	8 (3-24)	5 (2-9)	53 (21-91)
	6/6/24	Chinook	41 (25-58)	27 (16-39)	235 (142-338)	62 (38-89)	57 (34-82)
	Chum	1 (0-2)	0 (0-2)	4 (0-14)	1 (0-4)	1 (0-3)	8 (0-25)
	Sockeye	2 (0-7)	1 (0-4)	12 (0-38)	3 (0-10)	3 (0-9)	22 (0-68)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	43 (27-61)	29 (18-40)	252 (155-355)	66 (41-94)	61 (38-86)	451 (278-637)
6/10/24	Chinook	64 (42-89)	61 (41-85)	320 (212-447)	90 (80-126)	87 (58-122)	622 (413-869)
	Chum	9 (3-15)	8 (3-14)	44 (16-76)	12 (4-21)	12 (4-21)	85 (30-147)
	Sockeye	5 (2-10)	5 (2-9)	26 (9-49)	7 (2-14)	7 (2-13)	51 (17-95)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	78 (53-107)	74 (51-102)	389 (265-534)	110 (74-151)	106 (72-146)	757 (516-1,039)
	6/12/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	4 (2-7)	60 (26-109)	19 (8-34)	7 (3-14)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	0 (0-1)	7 (1-15)	2 (0-5)	1 (0-2)	11 (1-23)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	0 (0-0)	4 (2-8)	67 (28-122)	21 (9-38)	8 (3-16)	101 (41-184)

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Table 4 (Page 2 of 4).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
6/16/24	Chinook	10 (4-18)	83 (28-141)	274 (94-467)	47 (16-79)	26 (9-44)	439 (151-749)
	Chum	1 (0-3)	8 (0-22)	25 (0-74)	4 (0-13)	2 (0-7)	40 (0-119)
	Sockeye	2 (0-2)	13 (2-19)	44 (11-64)	7 (2-11)	4 (1-6)	70 (17-102)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	13 (6-21)	103 (46-163)	343 (152-539)	58 (26-92)	32 (15-50)	549 (245-864)
6/22/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	59 (7-157)	507 (64-1,358)	98 (12-261)	98 (12-261)	761 (95-2,037)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	10 (3-18)	82 (28-152)	16 (5-29)	16 (5-29)	124 (41-228)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	76 (7-210)	658 (61-1,824)	126 (12-351)	126 (12-351)	987 (92-2,736)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	0 (0-0)	144 (23-374)	1,247 (199-3,234)	240 (38-622)	240 (38-622)	1,871 (300-4,852)
7/1/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	112 (80-155)	548 (391-759)	75 (53-104)	187 (133-259)	921 (657-1,277)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	207 (137-280)	1,011 (670-1,371)	138 (91-187)	345 (229-467)	1,700 (1,127-2,305)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	253 (191-321)	1,236 (932-1,570)	169 (127-214)	421 (318-535)	2,078 (1,568-2,640)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	0 (0-0)	572 (444-707)	2,794 (2,170-3,455)	381 (296-471)	953 (740-1,178)	4,700 (3,650-5,811)
7/6/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	8 (4-12)	447 (235-647)	8 (4-12)	80 (42-115)	542 (285-786)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	10 (6-14)	563 (332-793)	10 (6-14)	100 (59-142)	683 (403-963)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	14 (10-18)	757 (560-998)	14 (10-18)	135 (100-178)	920 (680-1,212)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	0 (0-0)	32 (23-40)	1,767 (1,301-2,250)	32 (23-40)	315 (232-402)	2,145 (1,581-2,732)

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Table 4 (Page 3 of 4).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
7/7/24	Chinook	6 (3-9)	11 (7-17)	195 (112-290)	23 (13-34)	29 (16-43)	264 (151-393)
	Chum	12 (7-19)	24 (14-37)	400 (242-635)	47 (28-75)	59 (36-93)	542 (327-859)
	Sockeye	23 (15-32)	47 (31-64)	799 (526-1,088)	94 (62-128)	117 (77-160)	1,081 (711-1,472)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	41 (30-53)	82 (60-106)	1,395 (1,014-1,806)	164 (119-212)	205 (149-265)	1,887 (1,372-2,443)
	7/16/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	5 (1-12)	23 (3-52)	13 (2-29)	5 (1-12)
Chum		0 (0-0)	14 (8-21)	65 (36-94)	36 (20-52)	14 (8-21)	129 (72- 188)
Sockeye		0 (0-0)	25 (12-42)	114 (52-189)	63 (29-105)	25 (12-42)	228 (105-378)
Coho		0 (0-0)	4 (0-11)	19 (0-51)	11 (0-29)	4 (0-11)	39 (0-102)
Total		0 (0-0)	49 (22-84)	221 (98-375)	123 (54-209)	49 (22-84)	442 (195-752)
7/20/24 ²		Chinook	2 (0-5)	0 (0-0)	10 (0-29)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Chum	15 (8-21)	0 (0-0)	92 (48-127)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	107 (56-148)
	Sockeye	12 (4-19)	0 (0-0)	72 (23-115)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	84 (27-134)
	Coho	0 (0-1)	0 (0-0)	2 (0-7)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	2 (0-8)
	Total	29 (13-42)	0 (0-0)	176 (81-254)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	205 (94-296)
	8/5/24 ²	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
Chum		0 (0-0)	2 (0-5)	21 (0-47)	0 (0-0)	2 (0-5)	25 (0-57)
Sockeye		0 (0-0)	5 (3-7)	45 (29-62)	0 (0-0)	5 (3-7)	55 (35-76)
Coho		0 (0-0)	12 (4-19)	105 (36-168)	0 (0-0)	12 (4-19)	129 (44-206)
Total		0 (0-0)	19 (10-28)	171 (88-252)	0 (0-0)	19 (10-28)	209 (108-308)

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Table 4 (Page 4 of 4).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
8/10/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	3 (0-7)	0 (0-0)	1 (0-3)	4 (0-10)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	3 (0-7)	0 (0-0)	1 (0-3)	4 (0-10)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	16 (2-41)	0 (0-0)	8 (1-20)	24 (3-61)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	58 (3-138)	0 (0-0)	29 (2-69)	87 (5-207)
	Total	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	79 (16-162)	0 (0-0)	40 (8-81)	119 (24-244)
	Total ²	Chinook	125 (97-154)	370 (267-480)	2,641 (1,937-3,541)	441 (317-605)	581 (441-754)
	Chum	22 (14-32)	281 (208-356)	2,205 (1,771-2,656)	267 (212-322)	551 (426-675)	3,326 (2,640-4,019)
	Sockeye	32 (22-43)	433 (317-577)	3,658 (2,770-4,854)	483 (326-706)	847 (651-1,081)	5,454 (4,127-7,184)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	4 (0-11)	77 (7-166)	11 (0-29)	33 (3-75)	125 (10-275)
	Total	180 (147-236)	1,088 (865-1,350)	8,580 (6,975-10,703)	1,202 (915-1,579)	2,013 (1,649-2,452)	13,063 (10,616-16,191)

¹Geographic strata: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, D2 – Akiak to Bogus Creek

²Harvest estimates for 7/20 and 8/5 shown for documentation, but not included in above total by species (see text).

Table 5. Estimated minimum salmon harvests for drift gillnets by subsistence opening, species, and geographic stratum, 2023. Numbers within parentheses are 95% confidence limits.

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
6/12/24	Chinook	2,180 (1,470-3,087)	303 (214-405)	533 (405-679)	124 (96-155)	121 (91-147)	3,261 (2,508-4,160)
	Chum	502 (217-858)	44 (22-70)	37 (14-66)	9 (4-15)	15 (5-29)	607 (322-966)
	Sockeye	98 (27-198)	41 (22-65)	37 (16-61)	8 (4-13)	4 (0-14)	189 (108-295)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	2,781 (1,903-3,902)	389 (279-515)	606 (462-767)	141 (110-175)	141 (99-180)	4,057 (3,123-5,164)
	6/16/24	Chinook	2,195 (1,326-3,597)	1,172 (896-1,482)	2,329 (1,730-3,129)	324 (242-417)	103 (65-147)
	Chum	781 (409-1,177)	216 (155-280)	343 (233-479)	48 (33-66)	26 (6-52)	1,413 (1,006-1,848)
	Sockeye	280 (127-461)	219 (155-300)	306 (191-450)	43 (27-64)	6 (0-18)	854 (636-1,102)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	3,256 (2,222-4,876)	1,607 (1,263-1,998)	2,978 (2,247-3,944)	414 (315-529)	134 (89-195)	8,388 (7,048-10,315)
6/22/24	Chinook	2,901 (1,649-4,328)	1,402 (964-1,911)	2,342 (1,862-2,874)	843 (653-1,029)	462 (241-764)	7,948 (6,295-9,590)
	Chum	4,255 (2,570-6,034)	808 (502-1,229)	1,681 (1,248-2,261)	368 (185-598)	421 (296-571)	7,534 (5,747-9,463)
	Sockeye	3,913 (1,493-4,870)	1,137 (803-1,499)	2,577 (1,892-3,459)	224 (102-398)	115 (51-203)	6,966 (5,283-9,022)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	10,068 (6,390-14,278)	3,347 (2,365-4,524)	6,601 (5,403-8,089)	1,435 (1,104-1,773)	998 (628-1,449)	22,448 (18,172-26,835)
	7/20/24 ²	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	21 (12-30)	63 (36-90)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	83 (54-113)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	11 (6-14)	32 (18-42)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	43 (26-55)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	3 (0-5)	8 (0-16)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	11 (0-20)
	Total	0 (0-0)	34 (20-45)	103 (60-136)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	137 (92-176)

-continued-

Table 5 (Page 2 of 2).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
8/5/24 ²	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-1)	1 (0-2)	0 (0-1)	0 (0-0)	1 (0-2)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	10 (5-18)	37 (17-63)	10 (5-16)	4 (2-7)	62 (38-89)
	Sockeye	6 (6-6)	20 (3-49)	24 (7-49)	6 (2-12)	3 (1-6)	60 (31-100)
	Coho	6 (6-6)	205 (158-257)	702 (521-893)	179 (136-234)	74 (56-94)	1,163 (3975-1,369)
	Total	12 (12-12)	236 (179-295)	764 (577-969)	195 (149-251)	81 (61-102)	1,285 (1,085-1,508)
	8/10/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Chum	0 (0-1)	1 (0-1)	22 (7-43)	3 (1-5)	1 (0-2)	27 (12-48)
	Sockeye	1 (0-2)	2 (0-5)	103 (6-271)	32 (12-69)	10 (3-19)	148 (46-323)
	Coho	21 (8-37)	27 (20-34)	1,141 (862-1,454)	147 (107-192)	50 (36-64)	1,386 (1,101-1,708)
	Total	22 (8-38)	29 (22-37)	1,265 (988-1,555)	183 (150-222)	61 (50-73)	1,561 (1,292-1,862)
Total ²	Chinook	7,268 (5,543- 9,368)	2,874 (2,319- 3,460)	5,198 (4,348- 6,082)	1,288 (1,076- 1,494)	685 (454- 987)	17,313 (15,264- 19,713)
	Chum	5,533 (3,661- 7,384)	1,068 (741- 1,498)	2,081 (1,625- 2,658)	427 (245- 657)	463 (333- 613)	9,572 (7,585- 11,635)
	Sockeye	3,289 (1,855- 5,266)	1,397 (1,055- 1,787)	3,020 (2,321- 3,904)	307 (181- 478)	135 (71- 223)	8,148 (6,474- 10,299)
	Coho	21 (8- 37)	27 (20- 34)	1,139 (861- 1,454)	147 (106- 192)	50 (36- 64)	1,384 (1,100- 1,708)
	Total	16,111 (12,095- 20,692)	5,367 (4,352- 6,566)	11,438 (9,942- 13,044)	2,170 (1,828- 2,523)	1,333 (958- 1,777)	36,418 (31,807- 41,379)

¹Geographic strata: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, , D2 = Akiak to Bogus Creek

²Harvest estimates for 7/20 and 8/5 shown for documentation, but not included in above total by species (see text).

Table 6. Salmon harvests from both drift and set gillnets by subsistence opening, species, and geographic stratum, 2024. Numbers within parentheses are 95% confidence limits.

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
6/3/24	Chinook	4 (2-7)	1 (0-1)	32 (14-52)	8 (3-13)	5 (2-28)	50 (21-81)
	Chum	0 (0-1)	0 (0-0)	3 (0-9)	1 (0-2)	0 (0-1)	4 (0-13)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	5 (2-8)	1 (0-1)	34 (14-59)	8 (3-14)	5 (2-9)	53 (21-91)
6/6/24	Chinook	41 (25-58)	27 (16-39)	235 (142-338)	62 (38-89)	57 (34-82)	422 (255-606)
	Chum	1 (0-2)	0 (0-2)	4 (0-14)	1 (0-4)	1 (0-3)	8 (0-25)
	Sockeye	2 (0-7)	1 (0-4)	12 (0-38)	3 (0-10)	3 (0-9)	22 (0-68)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	43 (27-61)	29 (18-40)	252 (155-355)	66 (41-94)	61 (38-86)	451 (278-637)
6/10/24	Chinook	64 (42-89)	61 (41-85)	320 (212-447)	90 (60-126)	87 (58-122)	622 (413-869)
	Chum	9 (3-15)	8 (3-14)	44 (16-76)	12 (4-21)	12 (4-21)	85 (30-147)
	Sockeye	5 (2-10)	5 (2-9)	26 (9-49)	7 (2-14)	7 (2-13)	51 (17-95)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	78 (53-107)	74 (51-102)	389 (265-534)	110 (74-151)	106 (72-151)	757 (516-1,039)
6/12/24	Chinook	2,180 (1,470-3,087)	307 (217-410)	592 (464-743)	143 (110-177)	129 (97-157)	3,351 (2,609-4,270)
	Chum	502 (217-858)	45 (22-70)	44 (20-75)	11 (5-18)	16 (6-30)	618 (332-977)
	Sockeye	98 (27-198)	41 (22-65)	37 (16-61)	8 (4-13)	4 (0-14)	189 (108-295)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	2,781 (1,903-3,902)	393 (282-520)	673 (530-835)	162 (128-202)	149 (107-189)	4,158 (3,242-5,267)

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Table 6 (Page 2 of 4).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
6/16/24	Chinook	2,205 (1,337-3,606)	1,254 (985-1,574)	2,602 (2,004-3,393)	370 (284-469)	129 (87-176)	6,561 (5,374-8,126)
	Chum	782 (410-1,177)	224 (163-291)	368 (253-506)	52 (35-72)	28 (9-55)	1,454 (1,052-1,887)
	Sockeye	282 (129-463)	232 (167-315)	350 (230-499)	50 (33-73)	10 (2-22)	923 (710-1,176)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	3,269 (2,233-4,8901)	1,710 (2,558-4,276)	3,320 (2,558-4,276)	472 (370-591)	167 (118-229)	8,938 (7,548-10,779)
6/22/24	Chinook	2,901 (1,649-4,328)	1,461 (1,027-1,954)	2,849 (2,087-3,782)	940 (705-1,175)	559 (310-882)	8,709 (6,841-10,651)
	Chum	4,255 (2,570-6,034)	818 (512-1,240)	1,764 (1,18-2,351)	384 (202-621)	437 (310-587)	7,657 (5,826-9,604)
	Sockeye	2,913 (1,493-4,870)	1,213 (858-1,593)	3,235 (2,167-4,608)	351 (142-618)	241 (88-466)	7,953 (5,831-10,571)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	10,068 (6,390-14,278)	3,491 (2,513-4,696)	7,848 (5,947-10,243)	1,674 (1,246-2,166)	1,238 (781-1,788)	24,319 (19,584-29,504)
7/1/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	112 (80-155)	548 (391-759)	75 (53-104)	187 (133-259)	921 (657-1,277)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	207 (137-280)	1,011 (670-1,371)	138 (91-187)	145 (229-467)	1,700 (1,127-2,305)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	253 (191-321)	1,236 (932-1,570)	169 (127-214)	421 (318-535)	2,078 (1,568-2,640)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	0 (0-0)	572 (444-707)	2,794 (2,170-3,455)	381 (296-471)	953 (740-1,178)	4,700 (3,650-5,811)
7/6/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	8 (4-12)	447 (235-647)	8 (4-12)	80 (42-115)	542 (285-786)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	10 (6-14)	563 (332-793)	10 (6-14)	100 (59-142)	683 (403-963)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	14 (10-18)	757 (560-1,338)	14 (10-18)	135 (100-178)	920 (680-1,212)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	0 (0-0)	32 (23-40)	1,767 (1,301-2,250)	32 (23-40)	315 (232-402)	2,145 (1,581-2,732)

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Table 6–(Page 3 of 4).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
7/7/24	Chinook	6 (3-9)	11 (7-17)	195 (112-250)	23 (13-34)	29 (16-43)	264 (151-393)
	Chum	12 (7-19)	24 (14-37)	400 (242-635)	47 (28-75)	59 (36-93)	542 (327-859)
	Sockeye	23 (15-1,32)	47 (31-64)	799 (526-1,088)	94 (62-128)	117 (77-160)	1,081 (711-1,472)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)
	Total	41 (30-53)	82 (60-106)	1,395 (1,014-1,806)	164 (119-212)	205 (149-265)	1,887 (1,372-2,443)
7/16/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	5 (1-12)	23 (3-52)	13 (2-29)	5 (1-12)	46 (7-105)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	14 (8-21)	65 (36-94)	36 (20-52)	14 (8-21)	129 (72-188)
	Sockeye	0 (0-0)	25 (12-42)	114 (52-189)	63 (29-105)	25 (12-42)	228 (105-378)
	Coho	0 (0-0)	4 (0-11)	19 (0-51)	11 (0-29)	4 (0-11)	39 (0-102)
	Total	0 (0-0)	49 (22-84)	221 (98-375)	123 (54-209)	49 (22-84)	442 (195-752)
7/20/24 ²	Chinook	2 (0-5)	0 (0-0)	10 (0-29)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	12 (0-31)
	Chum	15 (8-21)	21 (12-30)	155 (105-201)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	190 (135-243)
	Sockeye	12 (3-19)	11 (6-14)	105 (50-149)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	136 (76-205)
	Coho	1 (0-1)	3 (0-5)	10 (0-19)	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	13 (0-24)
	Total	29 (13-42)	34 (20-45)	280 (178-368)	0 (0-0)	0 (30-0)	342 (225-439)
8/5/24 ²	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-1)	1 (0-2)	0 (0-1)	0 (0-0)	1 (0-2)
	Chum	0 (0-0)	13 (7-21)	58 (27-95)	10 (5-16)	6 (3-10)	87 (49-129)
	Sockeye	6 (6-6)	25 (8-55)	69 (44-96)	6 (2-12)	8 (5-12)	115 (80-156)
	Coho	6 (6-6)	217 (168-269)	807 (624-1,013)	179 (136-234)	85 (65-108)	1,291 (1,078-1,509)
	Total	12 (12-12)	255 (199-314)	935 (729-1,148)	196 (149-251)	100 (78-124)	1,493 (1,273-1,733)

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Table 6 (Page 4 of 4).

Opening	Species	Geographic Stratum ¹					Total
		A	B	C	D1	D2	
8/10/24	Chinook	0 (0-0)	0 (0-0)	3 (0-7)	0 (0-0)	1 (0-3)	4 (0-10)
	Chum	0 (0-1)	1 (0-1)	25 (9-47)	3 (1-45)	2 (0-4)	31 (14-54)
	Sockeye	1 (0-2)	2 (0-5)	119 (18-287)	32 (12-59)	19 (8-32)	172 (62-346)
	Coho	21 (8-37)	27 (20-34)	1,198 (911-1,523)	147 (107-192)	78 (44-119)	1,472 (1,162-1,826)
	Total	22 (8-38)	29 (22-37)	1,345 (1,063-1,652)	183 (150-222)	101 (64-144)	1,680 (1,388-2,016)
Total ²	Chinook	7,400 (5,665-9,523)	3,247 (2,698-3,846)	7,846 (6,744-9,077)	1,731 (1,491-1,986)	1,268 (994-1,589)	21,492 (19,199-24,057)
	Chum	5,561 (3,701-7,407)	1,350 (1,017-1,792)	4,290 (3,613-4,969)	695 (494-932)	1,015 (835-1,218)	12,911 (10,827-15,004)
	Sockeye	3,324 (1,888-5,298)	1,833 (1,466-2,221)	6,684 (5,481-8,174)	791 (559-1,063)	983 (772-1,258)	13,616 (11,337-16,323)
	Coho	21 (8-37)	31 (22-42)	1,218 (935-1,544)	158 (114-206)	83 (46-126)	1,511 (1,212-1,870)
	Total ²	16,307 (12,351-20,802)	6,462 (5,397-7,720)	20,038 (17,758-22,769)	3,375 (2,870-3,883)	3,349 (2,796-3,940)	49,530 (44,175-55,147)

¹Geographic strata: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, D2 – Akiak to Bogus Creek

²Harvest estimates for 7/20 and 8/5 shown for documentation, but not included in above total by species (see text).

Table 7. Minimum annual harvest estimates by salmon species from the Kuskokwim River inseason harvest estimation program, 2016–2024.

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2016-2023 Average
Chinook Salmon	28,019	8,630	20,870	40,120	23,210	21,630	29,950	21,055	21,492	24,186
Chum Salmon	27,398	54,420	43,570	7,170	5,590	4,220	3,630	11,929	12,911	19,741
Sockeye Salmon	25,026	24,080	23,320	13,400	6,710	23,600	25,400	28,936	13,616	21,309
Coho Salmon ¹	ND	7,425	1,511	NA						
Total Salmon	80,443	87,130	87,750	60,710	35,500	49,440	58,980	69,346	49,530	66,162

¹ND = No data pr insufficient data

Table 8. Key harvest characteristics of 12-hour openings on June 12 in all years where inseason harvest was rigorously monitored. These numbers correspond only to the mainstem Kuskokwim River from Eek to Akiak.

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2016-2023 Average
Drift and set effort	560	584	497	489	426	409	477	212	459	456.8
Total salmon harvest	5,290	5,620	7,250	8,650	3,820	3,680	5,800	1,387	4,009	5,187
Total salmon/net	9.4	9.6	14.5	17.7	9.0	9.0	12.1	6.5	8.7	11.0
Chinook harvest	4,460	2,400	5,230	8,040	3,240	3,260	5,300	908	3,222	4,105
Chinook/net	8.0	4.1	10.5	16.4	7.6	8.0	11.1	4.3	7.0	8.7
Chum harvest	610	2430	1770	310	460	70	60	96	602	726
Sockeye harvest	220	800	250	290	100	350	440	382	185	354
Chum/Sockeye total	830	3,230	2,020	600	560	420	500	478	787	1,080
Chum-Sockeye/net	1.5	5.5	4.1	1.2	1.3	1.0	1.0	2.3	1.7	2.4
Species ratio	0.2	1.3	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.4

Note: To allow comparisons to previous years, the 2023 and 2024 data only include characteristics from strata A to D1, excluding stratum D2.

Figure 1. Map of the Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge waters that comprise the survey area with geographic strata noted (A – E). Dashed lines indicate strata boundaries.

Figure 2. The (*left*) total estimated setnet trips by opening and (*right*) proportion of all estimated setnet trips that occurred in each geographic stratum by opening.
Note: Setnet effort not shown for all openings due to insufficient data.
 Geographic strata are: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, D1 = Akiachak to Akiak, and D2 = Akiak to Bogus Creek.

Figure 3. Total (*left*) estimated driftnet trips by opening and (*right*) proportion of all estimated trips that occurred in each geographic stratum by opening.

Note: Driftnet effort is not shown for all openings due to insufficient data.

Geographic strata are: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, and D = Akiachak to Akiak

Figure 4. Estimated salmon harvest by species in the openings for which data were collected; estimates include both drift and set gillnet harvests. Vertical lines are 95% CL bounds.

Figure 5. Total number (*left*) of interviews used to inform the harvest estimates from each opening and (*right*) proportion of all interviews that came from each source by opening.

Data sources were: BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC/KRITFC/USFWS), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), and CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 6. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 6/3/2024 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 7. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 6/6/2024 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 8. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 6/10/2024 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 9. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed driftnet trip interviews for the 6/12/2024 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 10. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed driftnet trip interviews for the 6/16/2024 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 11. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed driftnet trip interviews for the 6/22/2024 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 12. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 7/1/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 13. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 7/6/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 14. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 7/7/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 15. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 7/16/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 16. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed driftnet trip interviews during the 7/20/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 17. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 8/5/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC/KRITFC/USFWS), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 18. Distribution of relevant quantities from completed setnet trip interviews during the 8/10/24 opening, with means for all available interviews and by data source. BBH = Bethel boat harbor (ONC), FC = Bethel area fish camps (ONC), CBM = community-based harvest monitoring (KRITFC)

Figure 19. Total salmon harvest by species across all openers for which harvest estimates were produced including both drift and set gillnets, 2024.

Figure 20. Total salmon harvest by species and strata across all openings for which harvest estimates were produced, including both drift and set gillnets, 2024. Geographic strata are: A = below Johnson River, B = Johnson River to Napaskiak, C = Napaskiak to Akiachak, and D = Akiachak to Akiak.